

CULTIVATING THE NEXT GENERATION: INTEGRATING TRADITIONAL VALUES IN INFORMATION LITERACY EDUCATION

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Abstract

In the age of rapid information technology advancement, information literacy has emerged as a vital foundational skill in modern society. However, equipping students with merely technical and knowledge-based training falls short of addressing their holistic development, which necessitates the nurturing of correct values and comprehensive qualities. Chinese traditional values, a treasured spiritual heritage, hold profound ideological and political education significance. This paper endeavors to investigate the incorporation of these invaluable traditional values into the framework of information literacy curriculum construction. The aim is to enhance students' ethical and moral development, ultimately contributing to the cultivation of individuals who are not only well-versed in information literacy but also well-rounded, equipped to be builders and successors of socialism with Chinese characteristics, embodying moral, intellectual, physical, aesthetic, and labor-related development.

1. Introduction

With the rapid development of information technology, information literacy has become one of the important basic abilities in modern society. However, pure technology and knowledge training is far from enough, students' comprehensive quality and correct values are equally important. As the precious spiritual wealth of the Chinese nation, excellent traditional values have important ideological and political education significance. This paper aims to explore how to integrate excellent traditional values into the ideological and political construction of information literacy curriculum, improve students' ideological and moral cultivation, and make contributions to cultivating the builders and successors of socialism with Chinese characteristics with all-round development of morality, intelligence, physique, the United States and labor.

2. Information Literacy curriculum and new liberal arts perspective

Information literacy course is a course to cultivate students' ability in information acquisition, evaluation, organization and utilization [1]. It can improve students' ability in information acquisition, enhance their ability in information processing and innovation, and cultivate students' critical thinking and awareness of social participation to meet the needs of the information age.

The new liberal arts perspective is an important concept for expanding and developing traditional liberal arts education. Traditional liberal arts education emphasizes knowledge transmission and academic research, while the new liberal arts perspective places greater emphasis on humanistic care, critical thinking ability, and

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innovative spirit. In this new perspective, information literacy curriculum has also undergone some important changes.

First of all, the relationship between the information literacy curriculum and the new liberal arts vision is mutually promoting and complementary. The emphasis on humanistic care in the new liberal arts perspective makes the information literacy curriculum pay attention to the individual development of students, and pay attention to their emotions and needs. Through the teaching of information literacy courses, we can cultivate students' sensitivity to information and guide them to establish correct information values. At the same time, the learning process of information literacy courses can also cultivate students' critical thinking ability and innovative spirit, which is in line with the concept of new liberal arts vision.

Secondly, the new liberal arts perspective puts forward higher requirements for the ideological and political construction of information literacy courses. Ideological and political construction refers to guiding students to form correct ideological concepts and moral values through the process of teaching and learning. From the perspective of the new liberal arts, the information literacy curriculum needs to pay attention to the ideological and moral education of students, and guide them to establish the moral bottom line of correct information selection, evaluation and utilization. At the same time, the ideological and political construction of information literacy courses can promote the all-round development of students and further develop their sense of social responsibility and civic awareness.

In addition, under the new liberal arts perspective, the information literacy curriculum also needs to expand the research field and methodology. Traditional information literacy courses pay more attention to the use of information tools and the cultivation of technology, while in the new liberal arts perspective, information literacy courses should focus on the exploration of the meaning and value of information, the study of the social and cultural influence behind information, and improve students' deep understanding of information and critical thinking ability.

3. Problems in ideological and political construction of information literacy curriculum

In the ideological and political construction of information literacy courses, there are some problems that need to be paid attention to and solved.

(1) Inadequate understanding: many people have insufficient understanding of the significance and value of ideological and political construction of information literacy courses [2]. They often limit it to technical training and lack a deep understanding of ideological and political education. This lack of awareness makes the ideological and political construction of information literacy curriculum ignored and unable to play its due role.

(2) The problem of uniformed content: some information literacy courses only focus on imparting skills and knowledge in ideological and political construction, and lack the cultivation of students' values and moral cultivation. This kind of single content design neglects the development of students' comprehensive quality, which makes the ideological and political orientation of information literacy course unclear.

(3) Lack of emotional education: The ideological and political construction of information literacy curriculum often lacks attention to students' emotional education. Ideological and political education should pay attention to cultivating students' emotional attitude and sense of responsibility, but sometimes only pay attention to the indoctrination of knowledge, ignoring the cultivation of students' emotional experience and emotional value.

(4) Unreasonable method: some information literacy courses in the ideological and political construction of teaching methods are too rigid, single, lack of flexibility and heuristic teaching methods. This unreasonable method makes students lack interest and participation in information literacy courses, which affects the effect of ideological and political construction.

(5) Imperfect evaluation system: At present, the evaluation of ideological and political construction of information literacy courses focuses on the assessment of knowledge and skills, ignoring the evaluation of students' ideological and moral character and moral cultivation. The lack of a scientific and comprehensive evaluation system leads to a lack of comprehensive understanding of students' development in ideological and political fields.

(6) The problem of insufficient teachers: some regions and schools lack teachers in the ideological and political construction of information literacy courses, and lack teachers with experience and ability in ideological and political education. This brings difficulties to the integration of ideological and political education and information literacy courses, and affects the quality of ideological and political construction.

The key to solving the above problems is to strengthen the understanding of the ideological and political construction of the information literacy curriculum, and fully realize its importance to the growth of students and social development. In ideological and political construction, attention should be paid to the diversity and comprehensiveness of content design, and the organic integration of skill cultivation and value cultivation [3]. At the same time, it is necessary to attach importance to emotional education and focus on cultivating students' emotional attitudes and sense of responsibility in teaching. Flexible and diverse teaching methods should also be valued to enhance students' participation and enthusiasm. In terms of evaluation, it is necessary to establish a scientific and comprehensive evaluation system, paying attention to the development of students' ideological and moral character and moral cultivation. Finally, strengthen teacher training and ensure that there is a teaching team with experience and ability in ideological and political education.

By solving these problems, the ideological and political construction of information literacy curriculum can better play its value and role, promote the all-round development of students, guide students to establish correct ideas and values, and make positive contributions to the inheritance and development of socialist core values.

4. Ideological and political education value of excellent traditional values

Excellent traditional values refer to a series of core values, moral norms, and behavioral norms contained in excellent traditional culture. These values carry the wisdom and experience of the people and have important ideological and political education value.

(1) Excellent traditional values have a profound historical and cultural background, reflecting the wisdom and national spirit of the Chinese nation. By introducing these values for ideological and political education, students can better understand and understand Chinese culture, establish cultural confidence, and enhance their respect and protection of traditional Chinese culture.

(2) Excellent traditional values emphasize family ethics and social responsibility. Values such as filial piety, friendliness, patience and modesty have an important place in the culture. Guiding students to understand and inherit these values in ideological and political education can promote students to form a sound sense of family and social responsibility, and cultivate their spirit of caring for others and society.

(3) Excellent traditional values focus on moral cultivation and personal quality development. Values such as honesty, diligence and frugality, and abiding by moral norms play an important role in traditional culture. Through ideological and political education to guide students to establish correct moral concepts and moral standards, we can cultivate their good qualities of honesty, diligence and respect for others, and then improve their personal quality and social competitiveness.

(4) Excellent traditional values emphasize respect for the natural environment and life. Traditional Chinese culture emphasizes the harmonious coexistence between humans and nature, emphasizing the awareness of symbiosis with nature and environmental protection. Incorporating these values into ideological and political education can cultivate students' environmental awareness and sense of responsibility, and guide them to pay attention to environmental issues and actively participate in environmental protection activities.

(5) Excellent traditional values reflect the pursuit of humanistic spirit. The spirit of ancient literati pursuing moral realm and truth has become a treasure of traditional Chinese culture. Incorporating this pursuit into ideological and political education can stimulate students' spirit of exploration and innovation, cultivate their literary sentiment and aesthetic ability, and strengthen humanistic care and social responsibility.

Excellent traditional values have rich ideological and political education value. Through the introduction of these values, ideological and political education can help students understand and inherit traditional Chinese culture, establish correct family values and social responsibility, cultivate sound moral values and personal qualities, stimulate respect for the natural environment and life, and enhance humanistic sentiment and social responsibility. Through ideological and political education, these values can be better integrated into students' ideas and codes

of conduct, and provide strong support for students' all-round development and cultivation of social participation ability.

5. The path of integrating excellent traditional values into the ideological and political construction of information literacy curriculum

(1) Design of textbook content: In the information literacy course, we can introduce the content of excellent traditional values through carefully selecting textbooks and cases. For example, exploring Confucius' path of benevolence, the principle of integrity in Confucianism, and the stories of ancient wise people about moral cultivation. Such textbook design can help students better understand and feel the importance of excellent traditional values for individuals and society.

(2) Choice of teaching methods: The ideological and political construction of information literacy curriculum needs to pay attention to emotional education and interactive teaching methods. Through group discussion, role play and scenario simulation, students are guided to actively participate in discussion and thinking, and develop their sense of identity and understanding of excellent traditional values. At the same time, professionals, famous teachers or elders can also be invited to give theme lectures or share experiences, so that students can experience and feel the charm of excellent traditional values by themselves.

(3) Community practice and volunteer service: By combining information literacy courses with community practice and volunteer service, students can better feel the essence of excellent traditional values. Students can be organized to participate in community public welfare activities, such as helping impoverished families and caring for the elderly, so that they can experience the importance of values such as filial piety, kindness, and dedication in practice.

(4) Formulation of evaluation methods: The evaluation methods of ideological and political construction of information literacy courses should include the evaluation of students' value cultivation. In addition to traditional exams and tests, open-ended questions can be designed that ask students to analyze real-world problems in light of outstanding traditional values and demonstrate their understanding and ability to apply those values. At the same time, it can also be evaluated through the participation, initiative and social responsibility of students, so as to comprehensively understand the development of students in terms of excellent traditional values.

(5) Professional development and teaching improvement of teachers: In order to better integrate excellent traditional values into ideological and political education, teachers need to continuously improve their teaching ability and professional literacy. Through symposiums, research papers, visits and exchanges, teachers can strengthen their theoretical research and practical exploration of excellent traditional values, and improve their ideological and political building ability in information literacy courses.

Integrating excellent traditional values into the information literacy curriculum is a task that requires many efforts. Through the above paths, the excellent traditional values can be integrated with the ideological and political construction of information literacy curriculum, and the all-round development of students and the cultivation of correct values can be promoted. Such an organic combination of ideological and political education and information literacy will contribute to cultivating young people in the new era who have a sense of social responsibility and innovative ability to take on the great responsibility of national rejuvenation.

6. Conclusion

From the perspective of information literacy curriculum in the new liberal arts, this study explored the important position and value of excellent traditional values in ideological and political education, and proposed the path to integrate them into the ideological and political construction of information literacy curriculum. Through improvements in textbook content design, teaching method selection, community practice and volunteer service, evaluation methods development, and teacher professional development, students' comprehensive growth and the formation of correct values can be effectively promoted. The combination of excellent traditional values and information literacy courses will contribute to the cultivation of young people with a sense of social responsibility and innovation ability in the new era, and will also contribute to promoting the inheritance and development of Core Socialist Values. In the future research, it is also necessary to further deepen research, improve relevant

educational policies and practical exploration, and jointly promote the ideological and political construction of information literacy courses to achieve better results and results.

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- 2) 2022 Innovation and Entrepreneurship Development of Tourism School of Changchun University (JS2022041).

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